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The Vicissitudes of Foster Care in Interwar Yugoslavia and the Global History of Child Protection

Abstract: *This article deals with the possibilities and limits of rooting foster care in interwar Yugoslavia, which was primarily presented through a local project in Savska Banovina and reflected in a health film produced by the School of Public Health. The vicissitudes of foster care in Yugoslavia are set in the global and Balkan contexts, and in relation to interstate settings for child protection and its initial institutionalization as a strategy for legitimizing the new supra-national institutions of social work and post-1918 nations. The public representation of foster care to the international community and wider audiences in Yugoslavia is explored by examining the reports of Mica Trbojević, one of the main proponents of foster care, prepared for the First Balkan Congress on Child Protection (1936), and the film Spas male Zorice (1931 by Mladen Širola). Discursive practices aimed at promoting foster care are discussed in comparison to mainstream visions of families, children and rural communities, disseminated among Yugoslav and international experts.*

Keywords: *foster care; child protection; interwar Yugoslavia; international social work; childhood discourses.*

Based on the experience I've gained over the twenty years I've been working with the Grancher Foundation¹, I'd like to stress the great superiority of family placement over group placement in institutions. Not only is it less costly; it is also infinitely better for the child's physical, mental, and moral health. So, to sum up the opinion of almost everyone here, I think the best solution is to leave the child with the family, or with the mother, with guidance and supervision. If it is impossible to leave the child with the family because of conditions of contagion, as in the case of tuberculosis among parents, or because of poor moral conditions, foster care should be carried out in well-chosen families, supervised by competent visiting health practitioners. (Armand-Delille 1928: 1029)

¹ *L'Œuvre Grancher* is a philanthropic society first organized for promoting strategies to keep children in families in the case of tuberculosis among parents; foster care was one of the core instruments for implementing this mission.

This energetic remark, made by 50-year-old physician and bacteriologist Paul-Félix Armand-Delille during the heated debates concerning proper placement for ‘dependent’ children during the First International Congress on Child Protection in Paris in 1928, elicited mixed approval among the participants. Paul Strauss, Senator of the Seine, who led the session dedicated to the future of child protection, was even more extreme and translated the remark by Armand-Delille as opposition between “*familiale et ouverte*” and “*hospitalière et fermée*” assistance (*Congrès International 1928*: 881).

Seven years later, presenting her six-year project on foster care in rural families to the participants of the first Balkan Congress on Child Protection in Athens, Yugoslav pediatrician Milica Trbojević brought forward Armand-Delille’s argument and the case of the French experience, in an effort to promote foster care in Yugoslavia:

Institutions that require large capital to be founded and maintained are absolutely more expensive than family placement in rural houses. In the Seine department in France, there are more than 25,000 children who receive assistance; 20,000 are in family placement and only 5,000 are in boarding schools for infants and children. Why would our State, which is a poor rural country, not follow this example? (Trbojević 1935a)

Indeed, family foster care in interwar Yugoslavia largely remained the level of local projects and did not gain dissemination or even legitimization despite multiple efforts on the part of its proponents, namely, physicians, nurses, and filmmakers affiliated with the School of Public Health in Zagreb. In contrast to residential care of different types and the mass promotion of ‘mothers’ homes’ (a mid-term form of placement for mothers and their young children who are unable to live independently), foster care was only attempted in a pilot project in the Sava district. Searching for an answer to the question of what was behind the failure to introduce substitute families as an institution of child protection in Yugoslavia thus faces multiple challenges.

Generally, family foster care and its assessment have maintained an ambivalent position in the past and the present of child protection, which has directly shaped explanatory schemes regarding either the dissemination or the limits of foster care. On the one hand, foster caregivers have persistently been the target of public mistrust because of multiple cases of abuse and neglect. Moreover, rooting the idea of ‘attachment’ since the 1950s introduced more critical points against foster care as not sustainable for children who need long-term relationships. Remarkably, after

World War II, this critique directly transformed the agenda of *L'Œuvre Grancher* (Becquemin, 2005).

On the other hand, not adoption but professionalized foster care remains the most popular alternative to long-term placement in residential institutions, as one that is suitable for the most desirable scenarios of crisis intervention and family reunification. No other form of substitute care has generated so much debate about the balance between a professionalized, institutionalized and individualized approach to a child's needs. The vicissitudes of the history of foster care consistently embody the main dilemmas in child protection, including the very plausible conflict between the autonomy of parents and the safety of the child, or between the family's right to privacy and parental obligations toward community and society. Accordingly, the options and limits for disseminating foster care should be examined in both cultural and socio-political contexts.

Countries like Yugoslavia, with its complicated history of nation-building and international relations, present a challenge to existing typologies of child protection. It is no coincidence that in recent publications aimed at an international review of child protection, the countries that were part of former Yugoslavia are absent (Howard, Okyere 2022; Merke et al. 2019).² The spatial and temporal ambiguity of Yugoslavia and its successors prevents any attempts to develop a linear model of progress in child protection. There exists a strong impetus to revise typologies of child protection due to ongoing changes in approaches to refining the system which aims to ensure children's agency over their lives (Connolly, Katz, 2019). But there is another dimension along which to reorganize such typologies – one that is retrospective and targeted at better understanding the inception of child protection and the impact of the past on its ongoing functioning. The development of foster care in interwar Yugoslavia provides an ideal case for developing a historicized, thick description of child protection and its operation.

In this article, I bring into analytical focus the composition of driving forces behind the interwar trajectory of foster care as one that problematizes the role (and power) of different actors in rooting discourses on and practices of protecting children. First, I examine family foster care on the agenda of three international conferences on social work, in Paris (1928), Frankfurt (1932) and London (1936). Then, I move to the circula-

² Even in the most comprehensive collection of country cases, Berrick, Gilbert, and Skivenes (2023) there are no cases representing former Yugoslav countries.

tion of approaches to organizing child protection in the Balkans and explore the role of diverse geopolitical ‘schisms’, political divisions reflected in the contest between various interest groups, in interstate communication on child protection. Finally, I analyse the presentations by Trbojević at the first Balkan Congress of Child Protection and the film *Spas Male Zorica*, which elaborates the discursive practices concerning families and children brought forward to legitimize family foster care.

Foster care as hostage to the anti-crisis rhetoric concerning global child protection

Interwar global-level politics regarding children was built into intensive institutionalization of supra-national initiatives that often called for their legitimation (Boucher 2011). Prioritizing children was one of the ensured strategies not only to attract resources – from public attention to financial support, but also to generate such resources as solidarity – around the task to protect the future of humanity, children (Droux 2014: 379). Child protection has been one of the most consistent efforts to combat brutalization – first after World War I, and then as a counterbalance to growing anxieties about the impact of authoritarian regimes and the possibility of a new war. Pacifism and promoting broad-based humanitarianism were rooted in the rationalization of social policy (Boucher 2011). Along with abolishing the death penalty (Linde 2014: 545), care for children without parental protection operated as an important part of state consolidation and international order.

The attempts to fix increasing standards of childcare, along with a growing movement for collecting data regarding the state of the art of child protection, sharpened the critical view on family that had begun to be explored in terms of crisis. The reports and presentations from three international conferences on social work, initiated by the Red Cross and the international community of social workers that began to take shape in the last quarter of the 19th century, provide a rigorous overview of discursive practices on child protection. Like many other international projects of the interwar period, these conferences served the mission of informal diplomacy. Even the committees and initiators involved in the conference belonged primarily to the social-democratic wings of national and international political arenas,³ and the conferences intended to involve a range

³ René Sand, a Belgian social worker and physician, was the ideological inspiration for the conference to act as part of institutionalizing social work around the globe. The chair of the conferences was Alice Masaryková, daughter of Tomáš Masaryk, the first

of ideological approaches to social issues, operating in different countries.

Socialists and conservatives, representatives of Stalinist Russia, and an increasingly fascist Germany were sat in the same space, discussing the best ways to protect different groups among the population, especially mothers and children. For instance, the Yugoslav delegation to the International Congress on Child Protection, an integrative part of the Conference in Paris in 1928, consisted of a representative of the embassy of the Yugoslav kingdom Alexander Vukhević, Belgrade experts Matija Ambrožić and Miloš Popović, who reported on the event, Andrija Štampar, an expert who represented the School of Public Health in Zagreb, and Nikolaj Velimirović, bishop of the Orthodox Church eparchies of Ohrid and Žiža (Macedonia). The inevitable ideological oscillation at the conferences was dictated not only by the eagerness of the organizers to find the most appropriate position among those presented, but also by a desire to ensure the broadest legitimacy of the event and the acceptance of its later decisions.

The first conference was accompanied by a separate congress directly aimed at discussing issues of child protection and organizational solutions most appropriate for mass dissemination. The lives and health of children were discussed in term of the resources and proper politics for its sustainable reproduction. It explains why medical expertise dominated in discussions on producing standards of childcare. The issue of variety vs. universality in child protection was one of the central points of the discussions. Prioritizing universality emerged from different directions. One of the main patrons of the congress, the Save the Children Fund, promoted its priority through the principle of universality, according to which all children, regardless of nationality, race, or faith were entitled to their rights (Veerman 1992: 91).

Along with this rights-based rhetoric, the experience of large countries such as Germany or the Soviet Union competed against each other to present the most universal program of childcare. Not infrequently, the Soviet representative Vera Lebedeva,⁴ whose detailed report lasted more

president of Czechoslovakia, and the vice-chairs included Mary Abby van Kleeck, a U.S. social scientist and women's rights activist who shared a leftist view on labor, Cyrille Van Overbergh, one of the prominent politicians of Katholiek Verbond van België, and Anton Geiss, one of the representatives of the Social Democratic Party in Germany.

⁴ Vera Lebedeva (1881 – 1968) was a physician educated and working in Geneva before 1917. She was openly sympathetic to eugenics and a supporter of the legalization of

than one hour, presented the successes of child protection with the consistent motif of transferring positive experiences from centers such as Moscow and Leningrad to the periphery, especially Soviet Republics like Azerbaijan and the republics of Central Asia (Lebedeff 1928: 1018-1021).⁵ Clearly, the Soviet position, driven by the mission to point to the best set of universal decisions, questioned the intention of some experts, including that of the U.S. social worker Katharine F. Lenroot, who claimed in her presentation entitled “Social work for dependent children” that the individual needs of dependent children should be the grounds for making decisions concerning placement into an institution or a foster family (Lebedeff 1928 1014).

The debates regarding the variety and universality of child protection resonated with discussions regarding the proper definition of those children who needed protection. Predictably, the proponents of individualized child protection and foster care as a main strategy to ensure sensitivity to the child’s needs, criticized the definition of ‘dependent’ because of the risk of relegating the child’s individuality to the margins of professional care. Further, the position of proponents of a differentiated approach was not so resonant as that of the promoters of universalist organizational decisions, not least because of a clear medicalized view on child protection as aimed at preserving child health above all. Nutrition, basic hygiene, and the prevention of infectious diseases were the main issues discussed in the context of mothers’ employment and the economic instability of many regions across the globe. The professionalization of care and the emancipation of children from families by developing social and health services such as open-air schools, summer colonies, and other semi-residential institutions were seen as the most feasible and desirable organizational solutions.

Four years later, the conference in Germany directly addressed the impossibility of sustainable family life and called for understanding social work as an irreplaceable institution for less problematic dynamics of family units in various uncertain circumstances.⁶ The conference opened

abortion, especially in rural areas. Further, she was the first organizer of the governmental institutions responsible for the politics regarding motherhood and childhood.

⁵ Immediately after the conference the Soviet Department of Child Protection organized retraining for medical practitioners in Petrograd and offered the dissemination of the universalist Soviet model to Western colleagues. More in Susan Grant (2022).

⁶ *Program of the Second International Conference of Social Work*, Archive of the University of Keele, Institute of sociology, LP/6/3/1/.

with the report "The Family in a Changing World," by John Christian Pringle, one of the organizers of the first conference and a prominent member of the Council of the Eugenics Society, who developed family casework around the globe through his career as priest and educator. In response to the dilemma between a voluntary and individual supply of social needs vs. compulsory and collective social policy, Pringle highlighted the family or household "as the essential economic unit, and that, within the family, it is the housewife and mother, and not the wage-earner, who should be regarded as of paramount importance".⁷

The central and unique role of social work with mothers was discussed within a special session regarding 'broken homes', that is families that had lost their male wage-earners. Right-wing politician and economist Gösta Bagge declared that "the decline in the feeling of personal responsibility and the extension of public relief" threatened the existence of modern society, and, further, that "complete reorganization and reform of present social policy can alone avert impending disaster", and that what was needed was "a criticism based on popular psychology, and a social policy". Residential care or visiting services were discussed as the main organizational forms capable of coping with the problem of 'broken homes', and foster care disappeared from the radar of public attention due to general apprehension regarding family life as the best option for care.

The last pre-war conference in 1936 dealt with the issue of community and the recent changes in community life, volunteers' participation, and informal networking as resources for social care. British sociologist Alexander Farquharson, one of the pioneers of the sociology of communities who, together with his colleagues and students, collected multiple cases of community life around Europe, including Czechoslovakia, Bulgaria, and Yugoslavia, was one of the engines driving the conference. He offered to participants the opportunity to not just prepare their papers but to answer questions regarding their experience of cooperating with public, private, and philanthropic organizations, and to discuss different opinions.

The very probable risk of decreasing the involvement of community as a main resource for social work dovetailed with the increasing fear of authoritarianism. This emergent agenda resonated with the obvious priority of female participants. Even in the mass media, the third confer-

⁷ Later, this thesis was developed in the guidance, published with an introductory text by influential liberal politician Charles Mallet (Pringle 1933).

ence was presented as a forum for the most influential women from around the world. The institutionalization and professionalization of social work were discussed as processes with two – a positive and a negative – sides with regard to community life. R.H. Hazemann,⁸ who chaired the session aimed at discussing the perspectives of cooperation between social services and hygiene, stressed in his overview of country cases the role of networking and professionals as capable of connecting public and private initiatives. The replacement of informal connections between different parts of the community was also important for substitute family care because systematic institutionalization was evaluated as often 'squandering resources'.⁹

Within the same session Edward Fuller, one of the ideologues of the Save the Child Fund, presented a report about the Fund's achievements (Fuller 1936). The report clearly identified as worthy partners only the state bodies of countries evaluated as nascent in institutionalizing child protection – professionalization through introducing visiting services and residential as well as semi-residential institutions were claimed to be the most desirable strategy. Western voluntary organizations were seen as engines for the development of child protection in countries like Poland, Hungary, and Yugoslavia, and the willingness of national governmental bodies to provide conditions to implement the international recommendations represented the main positive outcome. Foster care was not among the priorities of the Save the Children Fund during the interwar period; it was not promoted as an organizational solution the way visiting nurses or short-term residential placements were. In 1951, Fuller published a book entitled *The Right of the Child: The Chapter in Social History*, which cemented these ideas within the international movement for children's rights.

Clearly, in terms of the global mechanisms of diffusion of new norms and standards, the dissemination of foster care during the interwar period did not achieve a global scope in contrast to summer camps for children or state support of nutrition for infants (Linde 2014: 553). It faced many obstacles in the efforts at coercive dissemination, even in the colonies of France, one of the rare promoters of foster care, not least because of clearly different cultures of family life. But to what degree was

⁸ Dr. Robert Henri Hazemann (1897 – 1976) a French physician, was a leading expert on hygiene in the League of Nations, also a proponent of a pronatalist prohibition on abortion.

⁹ *Report of Commission I Hygiene and social services*, 1936, Archive Keele University, fond of Institute of Sociology, International Conference on social Work LP/6/3/1/3/8.

the mechanism of principled activism in disseminating foster care, consistently represented in interwar France and based on the activism of physicians, to be found in the figures of the most respectful experts in child protection available for disseminating foster care in Yugoslavia? To answer this question, I reconstruct the participation of public health experts and practitioners in shaping child protection in Yugoslavia as part of the entangled history of child protection in the Balkans.

Child protection in the Balkans: An exaggerated mission of unity

In the Balkan countries, child protection evolved in the shadow of never-ending wars, which inevitably led to an increasing number of orphans and unaccompanied minors (Popova 2007). The very first attempts to move from private charity to the systematic protection of children in the late nineteenth century were directly related to the presentation of children and their destinies as the most complete embodiment of the horrors of war; child protection was contrasted to all the intense political violence. Establishing the Serbian Society for the Support and Education of Orphans and Abandoned Children (*Društvo za potpomaganje i vaspitanje sirote i napuštene dece*) was a response to the increase in the number of orphans after the Serbo-Turkish War (1876 – 1878) and was modeled on women's patriotic movements in France and Germany, which combined the protection of children with the defence of the fatherland (Izveštaj o radu Društva 1937).

Searching for unity represented a response to yet another challenge, multiple political “schisms”, political contests that coincided with geographical or ethnic divisions. This search should be seen not only as an extreme manifestation of local diversity but also as a particular geopolitical driving force behind any dimension of social policy, including child protection. The proponents of child protection teetered between different political camps, which explains the experts' desire for strategies that would be embraced by a given political movement. One of the notable examples of the impact of such political schisms is the addition of the defining term “patriotic” to the Foundation for Child Protection in Greece, a change that was supported by law (Vassiliki 2018: 85).

It is reasonable to assume that the functioning of child protection in the region was another light and positive side of nation-building, aimed at saving lives of future generations (Vassiliki, Karakatsani 2019). Child protection was consistently tasked with the mission to connect or even unite the nation through the systematic partnership even between those

ethnic groups whose relationships otherwise remained politically tense (Boucher 2011: 177). For instance, in 1920, the Society for the Support and Education of Orphans and Abandoned Children was transformed into the Society for Educating and Protecting Yugoslav Children (*Društvo za vaspitanje i zaštitu jugoslovenske dece*). Uniting with other organizations from Bosnia and Ljubljana, the mission was to “raise children in the same spirit of the future of Yugoslavia”, and to disseminate the use of residential institutions modeled after the *Dom sirotne dece* residential care institute (Izveštaj o radu Društva 1937: 103).

Uniting nations around child protection required the application of univocal and strong messages about saving children, and in the Balkans, child deprivation and its extreme manifestation, child mortality, became a predominant discursive practice: “Here we have to paint a terrible picture, that from 1920 to 1939 the nation gave birth to 85,755 stillborn children, that over 38,000 unfortunate mothers died during childbirth, and that over 1,150,000 infants died in this time period!” (Vidaković 1939: 22). Moreover, statistical data regarding child mortality in the region only buttressed alarmist rhetoric in all Balkan countries. During the interwar period, in comparison with other Central Eastern European countries, only Romania's infant mortality rate exceeded that of Yugoslavia, as well as that of Bulgaria and that of Greece (Vidaković 1937: 30).

The plight of children was contrasted to the indifference of public institutions, which should have been key to providing for children:

Genuine social protection for children in Yugoslavia will be required: caring for 1,090,000 extremely vulnerable children from 334,430 impoverished [*pauperizirovane*] rural households without land, livestock and agricultural implements, and protecting 2,760,000 vulnerable children from 1,595,024 rural households whose property is utterly unable to provide the sufficient income necessary for the normal upbringing of children from semi-impooverished rural families; take care of 364,370 socially disadvantaged and disabled children of unemployed parents in cities; ensure the protection of 72,000 minor apprentices whose bodies are exhausted to the point of convulsions and whose living conditions are turning into a real social crime; to care for 280,000 overworked young urban workers, protecting them from bodily exhaustion as a result of exploitation by employers who, in their indifference to life and sole care for profit, ridicule and destroy thousands of these poor children, yoked too early, suffocated in hellish and unsanitary workshops. (Vidaković 1939: 46)

This alarmist paragraph is one among many written by Slobodan Vidaković, at the time one of the most influential experts in child protection since the late 1920s. Vidaković collected data through questionnaires

aimed at assessing the needs of families with children in urban and rural areas across Yugoslavia. Along with painting “a terrible picture” (*strashna slika*) – a consistent motif, this expert offered an explanation for the situation, namely, the systemic lack of professionals such as nurses, physicians, and teachers, as well as organizational units targeted at providing for children’s needs. Notably, previous attempts to introduce child protection were defined as *bureaucratization*, not institutionalization, and the result of “occasional charity” (Vidaković 1939: 12). Neither family nor community were seen by Vidaković as capable of protecting children, and he offered a very vivid depiction of a civilizational deadlock for describing the inability of rural households to care for children properly:

Many of these surveyed dwellings represent the most primitive types of houses, non-cultural heritage mostly dating back to centuries of slavery under Asian conquerors.... But they are no less miserable than the so-called "today's houses" of our village, built mostly from compacted earth, from piles, plastered with mud, with a floor made of earth, low, without a ceiling, dark, mostly covered with straw, sod, or half-rotted boards. The rural farms represent for the most part a series of these huts, as if hell had dropped them from the clouds, without any foundation, sprouting in the garbage, like mushrooms. (Vidaković 1939: 42)

According to Vidaković, not family but rather belonging to a collective such as a school institution could ensure proper care and education. The introduction of child protection at the level of state-approved decisions was aligned with this trend of seeing children protected in institutions, and medicalized the assistance offered to them. The group of experts who promoted this approach was led by Matija Ambrožić, a Slovene pediatrician educated in Vienna, one of the ideologues of the Sokol movement in Yugoslavia. Ambrožić promoted the professionalization of care for children through introducing an institute for professional nursing, as well as residential institutions and ‘children’s colonies’, which replaced insufficient care on the part of biological parents. In the early 1920s, he founded the first colonies near Ljubljana and linked their functioning to the task of disseminating the institution of patronage nursing (*zaščitna sestra*) (Obzornik zdravstvene nege 1969a).

The training of nurses was another important task that required new institutional solutions. At the end of 1922, Ambrožić advanced the decision of local authorities to establish the Institute for Social and Hygiene Protection of Children (*Zavod za socialno-higienskozaščitno dece*), which started its operations in the middle of 1923 as a center for the vocational

retraining of nurses. In 1926, in Lukavici pri Damžalah, with direct lobbying on the part of Ambrožić, the first children's colony was established for infants and toddlers whose mothers could not take care of their offspring. The same year, together with his closest colleague, Antonija Šiffrerjeva (one of the first Yugoslav nurses who, with the support of the Rockefeller Foundation, was educated in Canada and the United States,¹⁰ and who accompanied Ambrožić from the beginning of his organizational initiatives), Ambrožić accepted an invitation by the Belgrade authorities to devote his accumulated experience to solving the situation of child protection in the country's capital (*Obzornik zdravstvene nege* 1969b). Ambrožić cooperated closely with other prominent Slovene agents who promoted child protection, including one of the leaders of a feminist movement, Alojzija Štebi, who consistently lobbied for the professionalization of child protection (Grubački, Selišnik 2023). This camp of experts produced a certain representation of Yugoslav child protection at the international level. In 1928 at the International Congress on Child Protection, it was Ambrožić who reported on the situation of child protection in Yugoslavia (Ambrožić 1928). In his overview of the international trends in developing maternal lactation, P. Lereboullet, who had followed the advice provided by Ambrožić, emphasized that Yugoslavia was moving "in the same direction but further ahead of the French legislators" (Lereboullet 1928: 159). After 1945, Ambrožić became an international expert on child protection, and until the end of the 1950s continued to represent Yugoslav child protection to international audiences.

By the end of the interwar period, residential care was the dominant option for placement for children with disabilities and those lacking parental care, as part of professionalizing childcare. At the same time, a few activists began to institutionalize foster care. How different were the dis-

¹⁰ According to Rockefeller Foundation records, File: "Schiffreer, Antonija (Yugoslavia) – DS Nursing", Šiffrerjeva received a one-year fellowship for improving skills and organizing nursing services between 1925 and 1926. She spent nine months at Toronto General Hospital studying nursing routines in obstetrics, medicine, surgery, pediatrics, and social service. The main part of her time in training was dedicated to social work with children in different circumstances, and she was also trained to care for patients with complex diseases. The theoretical grounds of mental health, organizing services, and obstetrics complemented her practical training. In the final months of her fellowship, Šiffrerjeva worked at Boston Hospital, learning how schools for mothers were organized, along with how to teach mothers healthy nutrition and posture, one of the priorities. Additionally, Šiffrerjeva directly participated in caring for children. Her supervisor mentioned that Šiffrerjeva was especially devoted to administrative approaches and collective forms of care.

courses regarding family and children they promoted? What were the main arguments in favor of a ‘substitute family’?

Foster care: A modest chance for nuanced child protection

Milica or Mica Trbojević (1894 – 1961), born in the Serbian village of Ličko Petrovo on Croatian territory bordering Bosnia, and a niece of Nikola Tesla, graduated from the medical faculty of Zagreb University in 1927 and in the same year began her career as a pediatrician in the State Children’s Dispensary (*Državni dječji dispanzer*). She then started collaborating with the government of the Sava district, where, under her tutelage, foster care for children was introduced. Her devotion to foster care, which stood in contrast to the mainstream ideas about child protection, cannot be explained by a single driving force. A combination of factors were at play: her interest in intervening in families with tuberculosis, her childhood experience growing up in a village, and her pro-feminist stance, combined with a belief in rural progress.

As Trbojević informed the Yugoslav organizers, participation in the First Balkan Congress on Child Protection offered a chance to present this experience and promote it (Trbojevic 1935b). She presented two reports, one entitled “The Role of the Peasant Woman in Rural Family Placement of Children” (*Le rôle de la paysanne dans le placement familial rural des infants*), which she presented within the first session and which was dedicated to the politics of care for ‘normal’ children with a particular focus on the role of the state, followed by another report entitled “The Peasant Woman: Guardian of the Stranger’s Child” (*La paysanne – gardienne de l’enfant étranger*) presented within the session on the cooperation between public health and local child protection.¹¹ Like Vidaković, Trbojević brought forward an unflattering comparison between Yugoslavia and countries beyond, or in the ‘civilized world’, stressing the necessity to overcome the issue of child mortality: “We must understand that the birth rate in our country is high (29.7%) but that unfortunately the mortality of children is also high (20%). Only Chile and Malta, whose statistics are disastrously higher, can be compared with us, especially with Bosnia” (Trbojević 1935a).

Trbojević vigorously employed the vocabulary of ‘state interest’ and defined child protection as an investment in the future of the state

¹¹ Premier Congrès balkanique de la Protection de l’enfance (1935). *Revue Internationale de la Croix-Rouge et Bulletin international des Sociétés de la Croix-Rouge*, Bulletin No. 200.

and the nation: “It is easy to calculate what the losses are to the state if the child dies, because it is known that an adult returns what was paid for him as a newborn” (Trbojević 1935c). However, she criticized Belgrade’s politics, for its focus on professionalization and for being irrelevant to the majority of the country. She utilized an analogy between those who promoted ‘improper’ solutions to prioritize residential care and spoiled children: “It is as if we gave a little peasant who would play with a worthless toy a precious and expensive toy [belonging to] a spoiled child – a toy that he will never again have in his life!” (Trbojević 1935a).

The call for modeling child protection as dependent on the social profile of the state was her main critical argument against the mainstream movement among her colleagues to adapt professionalization as the pathway to child protection:

The social structure of a state must shape child protection. This assistance must be quite different in agrarian countries than in industrial countries; it will be different in countries where most of the inhabitants live not in large towns but in the countryside... However, until recently, we did not care about the fact that we belong to a rural country, where more than 80% of the inhabitants are peasants. We worked according to methods that even industrial countries are giving up nowadays. (Trbojević 1935c)

In line with her enthusiastic view on the French experience, Trbojević called for adopting the French approach to foster care: “Our society must learn the methods that must be adopted to work along with the countries whose work on social policy takes priority” (Trbojević 1935a).

Along with refuting an irrelevant and too ‘urbanistic’ approach, Trbojević rejected the mainstream belief in the decay of community life and the decreasing role of rural community so often promoted by international experts: “In our country, which is rather agrarian, where there are many inhabitants on a small property and where there are even those who do not own property, it is very important that social policy is driven by the relationship that exists between the countryside community and the wider society” (Trbojević 1935c). According to Trbojević, foster care proved a source of enlightenment for the entire rural community, as well as cooperation between foster mothers and medical professionals, along with short-term training in proper care for children: “Allow for the peasant guardian to be educated, and then her acquired knowledge gradually becomes and passes on to her family and throughout the village”. Trbojević provided several examples of how disseminating foster care “im-

proves the livingstandards of the countryside, and thereby that of all the people” (Trbojević 1935c).

Along with this optimistic view on the symbiosis of foster care and community life, Trbojević was realistic in evaluating the deeply rooted public view on orphans placed into institutions as meaningless ballast:

Society has not been able to shake off the opinion that these children are parasites of the State and that the money spent on them is an unpleasant burden on the budget. Society is still primitive, the notion of social assistance is poorly developed, and education from the point of view of hygiene is in its early days (Trbojević 1935c).

She considered foster care a chance for recurring community life:

The money that is spent on the maintenance of these children returns in multiple ways to the State; not only does it return by producing a healthy generation, but it is given directly to the poor families, who through this money improve their own lives, raising the general [socio-economic] standards of the State, which is the best investment of money. (Trbojević 1935a)

Trbojević called for a more institutionalized support for foster care that would involve the administrative resources of local authorities, and not only those of charity organizations. Drawing on statistical data, she easily demonstrated the rupture between the demand for foster care and the ability to provide it. This deplorable situation was illustrated by an example from the most prosperous region of Yugoslavia:

In the region of Save, which is among the most civilized regions of our State and which is, in economic terms, among the richest, there are approximately 5,000 children for whom it would be absolutely necessary to take care of, but there are only 1,000 of these children that we assist, even when counting those who are sent for protection to different private charitable societies. (Trbojević 1935a)

She was aware that the prevailing view on foster care was critical because foster women (*prehraniteljice*) who took children in their homes for a certain amount of pay, were mostly poor themselves. Wealthier families rarely took in children and, if they did, they asked for amounts which single mothers – often employed as housemaids in such wealthier homes – could not afford (Dugac 2015: 73). Trbojević emphasized the role of sustainable financial provision for foster families, even for single foster mothers: “In poor environments such as ours, the monthly allowance received for child care, even if minimal, plays an important role in the budget of a farm house” (Trbojević 1935a).

While foster care maintained a bad reputation, which was often used as an argument for replacing it with professionalized, residential care, Trbojević brought forward the idea of cooperation between foster mothers and local public health officials as sufficient for proving the appropriateness of foster care: “Until now there has been no case to note of such a peasant/guardian who did not carry out the doctor's orders, which is not always the case with real mothers.” She connected this obedience to new progressive standards and the reality of remuneration for foster care: “This material contribution forces the woman to be very precise concerning all the orders of the hygienist, and she is much more precise than the real mother” (Trbojević 1935a).

Her convincing arguments concerning child care aligned with the systematic negation of a selective, eugenics-informed approach: “The opinion that infant and child mortality is simply natural selection has long been abandoned”. Trbojević even exaggerated this argument in her presentation within the main session: “We know that even the strongest child will die without the necessary care and that the weakest, on the contrary, will prosper if he has everything he needs and develops according to proper managed directions” (Trbojević 1935a). Like many of her contemporaries, she would accept the premises of negative eugenics after the point of reaching a certain standard of care: “If all children [lived] in such good conditions, only then could death be said to exercise physical selection” (Trbojević 1935c).

The main argument in favor of foster care over residential institutions highlighted the ‘naturalness’ of placing children in a rural environment, whilst inevitably objectifying the child: “This is the difference between foster care and closed institutions for children, which resemble a greenhouse where the plant grows under artificial heat, unable to withstand the slightest cold, while children in the countryside grow like flowers transferred to a better land” (Trbojević 1935a). The analogy between children and plants was one of many other instances of applying the discourse of the geo-body, indivisible from its locality and a part of collective practices. The idea of the geo-body was also applied to attempts to reinforce the opposition of foster care to the biological family: “Children adapt most easily to this environment and it is there that they develop best, physically and morally, like a plant transplanted into better soil. The child develops under the same conditions and he later expects to receive strength and vigor!” (Trbojević 1935a). As Thongchai Winichakul explained, “The geo-body supplies the new [forms of] objectification for

the beloved motherland or common soil and, reciprocally, acquires the human loyalty originally given to the soil" (Winichakul 1997: 133).

The analogy between foster families and soil that 'saturates' and 'roots' was reinforced by the consistent promotion of the geo-body of the foster mother as an "undoubted and invaluable force, an eternal capital of our peasantry life" (Trbojević 1935a). The mother and the environment represented the unity that provides for all the needs of the child; placing the child in a foster family was thus seen as finding an 'authentic' place for the child:

The child receives in the guardian mother and in the environment which surrounds him the equivalent of family life. The child develops surrounded by tenderness and love and does not even realize that destiny has taken away his maternal love. He grows up free in the sun and the wind and that's what awaits him in life too! He acquires knowledge and the notions necessary for all of life, and this is what we need the most. (Trbojević 1935a)

Improper care from the biological mother was explained by her unnaturalness and intractable resistance to being trained as a good mother. "It goes without saying that this villager mother must be provided with a certain education that does not cause any difficulties. You may even think that it is easier than when it comes to a real mother who remains under the influence of bad habits, superstitions, and sentimentality". Along with the idea of the geo-body as near the mystical power of authenticity, Trbojević brought forward arguments that attributed the potential of sustainability to the patriarchal order: "By placing children in the homes of peasants whose lives are well regulated physically and morally, the problem of assistance found its simplest and most ideal solution. The rural family with its patriarchal tastes best replaces the child's own family". The reliance on the patriarchal order did not contradict the idea of the rural woman as an engine of progress: "She does not stay behind the peasant husband at all, she deviates from him considerably and leaves him well behind" (Trbojević 1935a).

Justifying foster care in villages was substantiated by attempts to juxtapose natural resources, namely, the maternal instinct of peasant mothers defined "as more informed by natural instincts, including love for a child" and the ability to transform their parental experience:

The peasant woman, as the mother of someone else's child, has shown herself to be an excellent mother. She welcomes the child and takes care of him with great dedication and affection. She is the safest collaborator in medicine. Alongside caring for someone else's child, under competent supervision, with minimal material compensation, she also ed-

ucates herself from a hygiene point of view and applies the experience acquired to her own children, her family, and others. (Trbojević 1935a)

In this respect Trbojević exploited the approach to parents (especially mothers) as semi-professionals, an idea promoted by the School of Public Health in Zagreb: “And this is why in child protection, the peasant woman can be our most useful collaborator” (Trbojević 1935a).

In 1938, she was invited by the Department of Social Policy and People’s Health in Zagreb to develop foster care as a measure for solving the problem of children without parental care.¹² Unfortunately, even this modest chance for developing foster care was lost with the beginning of World War II. Trbojević was not totally alone in her ambition to repeat the success of French colleagues and to root foster care in rural areas. In 1931, among other films aimed at promoting various forms of substitute care, Mladen Širola who, like Trbojević, sympathized with the Croatian Peasant Party (*Hrvatska seljačka stranka*), made the film *Spas male Zorice* (Save Little Zorka), which tells the dramatic story of a young girl who has found happiness in her new foster family after years of suffering under an irresponsible caregiver.

Public representation of foster care in health films: The foster family as a unit in a new society

Films that problematize proper and improper care for children became one of the mainstreams of interwar cinematography in different countries, not only among educational films but also in entertainment. Two general trends, namely, the psychologization of children as protagonists through increased interest in the internal world of the child, and the pathologization of biological families (especially mothers), shaped the main trajectory for representing substitute care in the films. Behind these interrelated trends, it is easy to recognize the outstanding influence of Ellen Key, the Swedish activist and child welfare theorist who was one of the pioneers in introducing children into public discourse as the subjects of their own actions. In her multiple publications, including the most famous *The Century of the Child* (1909) translated into many European languages, Key insisted that children had the right to choose their parents. This idea was enthusiastically accepted by Western promoters of

¹² Ministarstvo socialnoj politike i narodnog zdravlja The Letter to the Hygienic Institute of Zagreb 1938 HR-HDA-890. Collection of personal records of civil servants (Zbirka personalija), series Medical personnel, a dossier of Milica Trbojević.

foster care (Macinai, 2016). In 1926, director Gerhard Lamprecht, who had already attained a reputation for presenting children who rebel against the arbitrariness of adults, filmed the story of three children who reject their biological family and expose cruelty on the part of both biological parents and substitute parents until they either die or meet parents who love them and whom they choose (Dussel 2017). The film entitled *Die Unehelichen (The Children of No Importance)* was made with the direct support of the Association for the Protection of Children against Exploitation and Mistreatment (*Vereins zum Schutze der Kinder gegen Ausnutzung und Mißhandlung*).

Die Unehelichen focuses on the slim chances of a child surviving without appropriate care, as well as the practices of controlling the quality of child care in the family, both substitute and biological – practices which were only beginning to be institutionalized in Germany at the time. Social drama, on the verge of tragedy, introduces the norms that began to be promoted by international organizations during the interwar period: that the biological family is not always the best ‘natural’ solution for care, that the child should have a proper childhood with full access to consistent health care, healthy nutrition, attentive caregivers, sports activities, time spent with peers, and collective games. The film consistently constructs the idea of abuse and neglect as inevitable in the opaque space of the family which lacks proper scrutiny from helping professionals. And although, as in other films, Lamprecht builds the intrigue of the plot around the rebel child, the ability of children to take the position of active agents in their destinies is presented as a unique and not always reliable way to save a child. Through the different destinies of three children of different ages and genders, Lamprecht consistently promotes a positive attitude to intervention on the part of authorities: thoughtful and kind policemen, judges, and public health workers.

Širola, the director of a puppet theatre, founder of the first Yugoslav children’s theatre, and an active promoter of children’s culture, was undoubtedly aware of these trends and films.¹³ It is fair to interpret *Spas male Zorice* as a kind of adaptation of *Die Unehelichen*. Moreover, Širola was likely inspired by another famous Western film, *The Kid* by Charlie Chaplin. Širola reproduced the same plot as Lamprecht, with a focus on saving a child from death, but he radically changed the hermeneutic code.

¹³ For example, Ellen Key's ideas and writings were extremely popular in interwar Italy, and their influence on the cultural and social life of Croatia remained enormous; more in Hällström, Jansson, Pironi (2016).

Lamprecht's drama is transformed into eccentric comedy: Jitrička, an irresponsible caregiver, drinks from morning to night, according to the subtitles, and she is always unstable. To demonstrate her instability, Širola chooses one of the favorite techniques of classic film comedy – constant amusing falls that emphasize the awkwardness of a would-be drunkard. In contrast to the dramatic story of abuse and death told by Lamprecht as a warning, Širola tries to impose upon the audience a hostile and sarcastic attitude towards an unkempt, selfish, and greedy guardian. This inversion clearly relies on intertextual pleasure – the audience in Zagreb and other Yugoslav cities was familiar with the films by Lamprecht, as well as with classical comedies. Širola drifts away Lamprecht's devotion to the child's subjectivity as an engine of proper substitute care and brings forward the role of the substitute family as the engine of healthy community life.

All of Širola's films present substitute care, whether foster family or residential large-scale institutions, as the best possible milieus in which to nurture proper childhood for nations. Generally, each of the films can be interpreted as a story of the transformation of the child protagonist, who at the beginning of the film is a lost child, abandoned by the very institution that should be protecting them, into a collective child within the most powerful institutions intertwined with the nation. In *Spas male Zorice*, ten-year old Zorka is being abused by a chronic alcoholic, Jitrička, who for unknown reasons has been entrusted with her care. The portrayals of Zorka's experience of improper care includes being forced to beg and her health needs being neglected. The begging scene in the Marija Bistrica, one of the main places of pilgrimage in Croatia, on the Feast of the Assumption of Mary, can be easily interpreted as the culmination of Zorka's alienation from the nation and from collective childhood; she is unable to participate and can only beg. In despair, and in fear of her guardian, who beats the girl and leaves her to sleep on the porch, Zorka runs and finds herself in an ideal foster family, which already has two children. Foster parents not only patiently teach the girl hygiene skills and take care of her health, but also create the conditions for a childhood full of games and preparation for adult life.

The film consistently juxtaposes a child protagonist with good parents and a child protagonist with 'improper' parents via the image of healthy habits in the first context and unhealthy habits in the second. It is noteworthy that Zorka's unhealthy decision to spend the reward given to her on sweets leads to her last meeting with Jitrička, who dies at the end of the film. 'Improper' childhood manifests in the unavailability of enter-

tainment for children and in the suppression a child's 'natural' curiosity. Children's entertainment and attractions such as a carousel are observed by Zorka with undisguised interest and envy. The film emphasizes the lack of a peer environment which living with an unsuitable guardian entails, contrasted to the intensive communication with peers after appropriate placement. The round dance scene in which the child protagonist who has found stable care joyfully participates, is a motif reproduced in each of širola's films. This dance symbolizes the transition of the former orphan, alienated from the people, into the collective child of the nation.

In this film, a girl changes not only her foster family but also her entire village. The film begins with an intervention by neighbors who try to prevent Jitrička's attack on Zorka, and several times the attempts of the community targeted at protecting Zorka are unsuccessful until she escapes and finds new family. If in her previous village, the neighbors were not consistent in their help, and despite the doctor's attempts the girl fails to receive proper care, in the new family living in another village mutual assistance and understanding are the main resources. With proper foster care, Zorka starts her integration into the community and more broadly speaking, into the nation. This message is conveyed through consistent reproduction of the image of the geo-body: children in the foster family are miniature copies of their parents, dressed in the same clothing and assuming the same posture, and so on. Notably, Jitrička can't be seen as a representative of the geo-body; mostly, she is depicted as somebody who has lost the connection with tradition and authentic soil. The scene featuring the death of Jitrička, who dies surrounded by young, vibrant, and stable women in national costumes, only reinforces this contrast.

Spas male Zorice was one of the most well-promoted films produced by the School of Public Health, impacting local campaigns in favor of a more humanistic treatment of children (Shmidt, Kaser 2023). A fragment of *Spas male Zorice* was included in an overview film, *Borba protiv bolesti putem filma (Fighting Disease with the Help of Film, 1934)* prepared by the School to be screened at different international events. It is worthwhile to further explore the possible influence of the Yugoslav film on Henri Grignon's film *La préservation de l'enfance de la tuberculose par l'Œuvre Grancher (The Preservation of Childhood from Tuberculosis by the Work of Grancher)*, which was made in 1936 with the same goals as *Spas male Zorice* – to promote foster care to a wide audience. Like the Yugoslav film, the French production deviated significantly from the discursive practices promoted by Lamprecht and earlier pro-

ponents of foster care. This very possible post-film life of *Spas male Zorice* sharpens the question regarding the impact of foster care in Yugoslavia and the criteria for assessing its historical role.

Conclusion

Historicizing foster care in interwar Yugoslavia raises many questions regarding the divergence between the clearly complicated past of child protection and our very limited knowledge of it. Furthermore, the internally contradictory position of foster care and its ambivalent influence problematize approaches to interpreting the interrelation between ideas and practices aimed at promoting the interests of children.

The image of the collective child as embedded in the nation and an understanding of foster care as the return of the child to the fold of the nation was at the core of the ideology advanced by Yugoslav proponents of foster care. With the inevitable shift in attention to the relationship between the child and the foster parents, the promotion of foster care found itself in conflict with, or even challenging, mainstream discursive practices based on a vision of children needing to be institutionalized or even emancipated from previous 'backward' generations. This conflict aligned with the ambiguous position of foster care at the global level. In the process of intensive legitimization of their activities, international organizations focused on developing universal models of child protection. The forms of child protection desirable for organizational actors such as the Save the Children Fund would ostensibly represent a successful balance between the utopia of an individual approach and the uneasiness international bodies felt towards accepting the realities of selective approaches undertaken by large-scale institutions.

As an organizational approach in the interwar period, foster care operated as alternative model of medicalizing child protection, which was among the central trends in the institutionalization of child protection across the globe. Neither physicians nor nurses in mothers' homes or children's colonies, but mothers themselves were the agents of such medicalization. Accepting foster care as a semi-professional and semi-parental practice that successfully responded to the binary opposition of family vs. professional care remained beyond the priorities of interwar social work. It is clear that the fragmented development of foster care influenced the further evolution of models of child protection toward the predominance of large-scale institutions as a solution for children with disabilities or without parental care.

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